

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF SLAVE TRADE FROM THE WEST AND EAST

By

Prof. A. I. Yandaki
Department of History
Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto

&

Dr. Umar Muhammad Jabbi
Department of History
Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto

Abstract

Scholars have shed so much ink trying to document the European propelled Atlantic Slave Trade, but comparatively little attention has been given to Eastern Slave Trade in Africa. The recent upsurge of interest among some European scholars on the topic of Arab Slave Trade is ideological. Having failed to succeed in transferring the blame of Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade on African Kings and Chiefs; they now sought to invent another scapegoat to divert African criticisms and to overshadow the demands for reparations for European enslavement of Africans. This paper intends to briefly examine the two different slave trading activities, with the aim of presenting a comparative study. It will be shown that both in terms of numbers of slaves and in devastation brought to Africa, the Eastern Slave Trade in Africa is in no way comparable to the Trans- Atlantic Slave Trade. The Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade was pursued for the purpose of capitalism and it finalized with the imperialist conquest and forceful domination of the continent. The paper will also re-echo the reparation debate and stress the need for Europe and America to pay reparations to Africa in quite similar manner that the Jews and American Japanese were compensated for various injustices meted out on them during the Second World War.

Introduction

Slavery has been an important phenomenon in human history. It has been found in many places including

Asia, Europe, Africa and America from classical antiquity to very recent times. Africa's prominence in this history derives from the role it played as a major

supplier of slaves for ancient civilizations, the Arab world, Europe and America. The origins of slavery is lost to human memory, but it is highly probable that the emergence of class differentiation among human societies as well as perceived labour shortage on the part of the new privileged class must have given rise to conditions in which the less privileged class were reduced as servants to the wealthy.

Slavery is a condition in which one human being is owned by another person. It was a form of dependent wageless labour performed by a non-family member. A slave usually had fewer rights than his owner or other free individuals, however, in Africa and among Muslim societies slaves did rise to position far above some ordinary free individuals. A number of traditional titles usually reserved for slave families in Muslim Northern Nigeria palaces is a case in point.¹

Slaves were generated in many ways. Apart from normal master and servant relationship which often graduated into a form of domestic slavery as was the case in Africa, slaves were mostly victim captured in war, kidnapping, slave raiding and or piracy expeditions. There were also instances where people were enslaved as a punishment for crime or debt.²

Africa's contact with the outside world created a market in which one of the major articles of trade was the African slaves. Starting from the Arab Slave

Trade which transpired for about fourteen centuries, to the European propelled Atlantic slave trade which though lasted for only four centuries but produced more drastic and more lasting effects on the continent. The following section will consider these episodes in some detail.

Africa's Involvement in the International Slave Trade

As already indicated above, Africa was involved in two types of international slave trade. The first of these trading relations was the one established between Africa and the Muslim world across the Sahara, the Red Sea and the Indian Ocean. Gold and slaves provided the life blood for this trade.³ Other articles of trade include silk, horses, ostrich feathers, cloth, copper beads, books and etc. The antiquity of slave trading activities and other forms of contacts between sub-Saharan Africa and the North towards the Mediterranean is evidenced by the fact that, the Carthaginian army that raided Sicily in the 5th century B.C is said to comprise of people of Negroid character.⁴ However, it was reported that, their successors, the Byzantines used European and Asian slaves who were believed to be better adapted to the Mediterranean climate.⁵

The Muslim Arab defeat of the Byzantines in the areas of North Africa in the 7th Century A.D gave them control over the ancient trade between the opposite shores of the Mediterranean. Ibn Haikal writing on the Magrib in the

10th Century A.D described it as ‘Remarkable for black slaves... (The white slaves come from Andalusia) and coral and embargos, and gold and honey and silk and seal-skins.’⁶ The earliest external slave trade was the Trans-Saharan trade. Although there had long been some trading up the Nile River and very limited trading across the western desert,⁷ the transportation of large numbers of slaves did not become viable until the 10th century when camels were introduced from Arabia.⁸

African slaves were mainly bought by Berbers and Arab merchants of the present day areas of Morocco, Algeria, Libya and Egypt. The Trans-Saharan Slave Trade was undertaken along six major routes: one went north from Ghana to Morocco; another stretched north from Timbuktu to Tawat in southern Algeria. The route that linked Hausaland to the traffic passed from the Niger valley and Hausa towns through the Air massif to Ghat and Aghadames. A central route linked Chad region to Murzuk (Libya). This is one of the most important routes in slave commerce, as it offered oasis at regular intervals that could satisfy Caravan water needs.⁹

The eastern sub-Saharan slave trade involved mainly maritime routes across the Red Sea. The Red Sea ports served the Ethiopian highlands and the Nile valley.¹⁰ In terms of volume, the Arab Slave Trade involved a steady but relatively small flow over a millennium and despite occasional high levels for specific points, there was not the

sustained volume in slaves that characterized the Atlantic Slave Trade at its height.¹¹ In fact, for a very long time, the Arab Slave Trade appeared to have been a supplement to a much more profitable commerce in gold and precious metals as well as other rare and exotic products of African states.¹²

An area of so much disputation among scholars had been the issue of the number of slaves involved in the African slave trade from the East across North Africa. Owen Alik Shahada, the author of ‘African Holocaust’, estimated the number of slaves involved in the trade to about 10 million and argued that the trade only boomed in the 18th century before which it was only a trickle.¹³ Similar observations were made, most particularly with regards to the Trans-Saharan Slave Trade (which also happened to be the busiest) by the authors of *Encyclopaedia Britannica*, 2008, that considering the problems involved in marching slaves across the Sahara with its scarce and widely separated water resources, it is generally doubted if the Trans-Saharan Slave Trade could ever have transported more than 6000 or 7000 slaves a year up to the mid- 17th century.¹⁴

A more meticulous and detailed statistics of slave transactions are the ones presented by Ralph Austen, Murry Gordon, Ronald Segal and P.E. Lovejoy.¹⁵ These estimates revealed that the total number of slaves taken from Black Africa for the period during which

the trade transpired was roughly about 11 million.

Table 1: Showing the Number of Slaves involved in Arab African Slave Trade.

Period	Trans-Saharan	Red sea	East African Coast
7 th C -16 th C	4,820,200	1,600,000	800,000
17 th c	700,000	100,000	100,000
18 th c	700,000	200,000	400,000
19 th c	1,200,000	450,000	442,000

SOURCE: R. Segal, *Islam Black Slaves: The other blacks*. Accessed from <http://www.amazon.cpm.islambblackslaves/dp/0374527970#reader.asat12thFebruary,2012>. Also 'Historical body cover' Twentieth century Atlas, Accessed from <http://erols.com/mwhite28/warstarv.htm.asat12thFebruary,20>

However, some Euro-Christian scholars committed towards de-emphasizing the horrors and negative effects of the Trans-Atlantic slave trade have sought to magnify every issue concerning Arab African slave trade and have fabricated exaggerated figures. The Christian Action Magazine, for example, concocted a figure as high as 180 million Black slaves. To demonize the Arabs the more, a mortality rate of about 80 to 90 percent of the slaves taken was fabricated,¹⁶ down-playing the business acumens of the Arab traders. For how could they afford such huge losses and have a viable trade?

The trade between Africa and the Arabs was never a one-way traffic. In return for their exports of gold, slaves, ostrich feathers, and other luxurious items, people of sub-Saharan Africa received articles like salt, cloth, copper beads,

weapons, horses and books. The African Kingdoms which participated in the trade experienced great prosperity. The economic benefits generated from the trade and taxes levied on goods passing through the various kingdoms enabled rulers to employ full-time administrators and support large armies.¹⁷

Furthermore, this trade created a coterie of literate African Muslims who were employed by the various chiefs in their palaces as secretaries. As did observe Crowder, even non- Muslim rulers like the Asantehene, employed literate Muslim Africans in their administration, not Africans trained by Europeans. This was because they were not available.¹⁸ Europeans only introduced the colonial school system when they saw the need to train Africans to help them in the domination and exploitation of the resources of the continent.¹⁹

The African slaves taken to North Africa and other parts of the Arab world were invariably used as domestic slaves, and in a few cases were engaged in cultivating the land in agricultural estates as was the case in Morocco and the Islands of the Mediterranean.²⁰ In addition, slaves were used in the military as warriors and carriers and some in the running of the government as messengers' retainers at court of rulers, and those that were fortunate enough to acquire advanced Islamic education, were appointed as officers of the state.

The Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade

The international human traffic that triggered tremendous consequences for the African continent was the European propelled Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade. It initiated the economic marginalization of the continent by depriving it of its manpower. The Atlantic Slave Trade unlike earlier forms of slavery was the first form of slavery that was solely motivated by commercial incentives. And it was unprecedented in scale. Millions of able bodied Africans were taken out of the continent within just a few centuries, for the development of Europe.

Portugal was the first country in Europe to enter the slave trade with Africa. We have a good record of some slave activity in 1441. Prince Henry, Son of king John 1 of Portugal, sent a Sea Captain named Antam Gonçaves to Africa. Henry had ordered his Captain to bring back animal skins and palm oil. Gonçaves thought

his Prince would be pleased if the trip also brought back some people from the African Coast. He returned to Portugal with some African captives.²¹ One of the captured men said that he was a member of the ruling family of his tribe. He asked for his freedom and promised to send back five or six other black men in his place. Gonçaves sailed back to Portugal with the prisoners. He went back with- "Ten blacks, male and female". They became slaves in Portugal. The Portuguese soon learnt how lucrative it could be to enslave and sell Africans. During the Sixteenth century, Portugal dominated the West African Slave Trade. Later, other European powers joined the rush for slave labour, for the exploitation of Mines and Plantations in the New World.²² By the second half of the 17th century, some European slaving companies like the British Royal African Company, the Dutch East India Company, the Danish Guinea Company, the French Senegal Company among others were formed and given royal charters to facilitate and regularize their murderous slaving project and reinvest their ill- gotten proceeds in their respective countries.²³

Many scholars have written about how Europe ransacked the African continent in search of labour and help for the Agrarian revolution in the Americas and the Industrial Revolution in Europe simultaneously. Therefore, considering the mass of literature on the subject, only a brief summary on the conduct of the trade will suffice.

In contrast to the exaggerated collaborative role of African rulers in the trade found in many Western literatures, a number of African rulers used every means at their disposal to protest the enslavement of their subjects. The case of King Nzinga Mbemba of Kongo Kingdom is worth emphasizing here. He had converted to Christianity and remained very close to the King of Portugal. And when he came to power in 1506 A.D seeing the devastation the slave raiding activities of the Portuguese was causing, he protested strongly through a letter written in 1526 to his "brother", the King of Portugal that Portuguese slave traders were robbing him of possessions and carrying his people into slavery.²⁴ Similarly, two centuries later, Agaja Trudo of Dahomey in protest to the enslavement and transport of his people outside his territory, offered to allow Europeans to establish plantations along the coast if they would cease to raid and enslave his people.²⁵ Another example of protest against the European slave trade was that of Almamy of the Imamate of Futa Toro who passed a law prohibiting the passage of slaves through his territory for sale abroad.²⁶ These and similar protestations could not find audience because slave trade before the early part of the 19th century was a central part of the commercial system of the western world.

Africa was not, as presented by some scholars, a reservoir where slaves were plentiful for anybody wishing to buy.²⁷ In fact, Europeans had to employ a number of dubious means to obtain

slaves. In most cases, they tried to stimulate a demand for European goods of exchange such as rifles as well as by exploiting the tribal and religious divisions and the incipient class contradictions within Africa.²⁸ In fact, in some situations, the Europeans got directly involved in the African warfare and trade networks as was the case in Angola, Mozambique and certain parts of Guinea.²⁹ It is however not deniable that some African chiefs did get directly involved in the sale of their citizens to the Europeans with the hope of getting European articles, most importantly rifles and gun powder. Possession of rifles was critical to the defence and expansion of territories of states.

The European Merchants took all the necessary precautionary measures to ensure that only healthy and able bodied humans who had survived smallpox and so have acquired immunity from the dreaded disease of the time were taken.³⁰ The acquired slaves were then subjected to a crude and horrendous treatment to ensure that the goods were "as per invoice". They were stripped branded with red hot iron, crammed and chained. They were then pushed into airless under decks in stifling misery and sailed for the America.³¹ During this harsh period of sailing it is reported that "one in every six capture died on the voyager."³² In addition, along the Middle Passage across the Atlantic, there were reports of brutality to discourage revolts. The series of slave revolt during Atlantic crossing³³ and the level of damage inflicted upon European slave merchant vessels is a

clear indication that, the Africans did not simply submit to the European merchants of death.³⁴

In return for the slaves, the Europeans brought in riffles, gun powder, chains, padlocks, buckets and various crude gadgets to Africa meant to stimulate the capture of slaves by exacerbating local squabbles between neighbouring states. Other imports were glassware, cloth, brandy and assortment of wines.³⁵

For more than four centuries (from the end of the 15thc to the 19th), the slave trade built the prosperity of West European nations. While this was going on, serious depopulation was taking place in Africa. According to the authors of *The Twentieth Century Atlas*, between thirty and sixty million Africans died while being enslaved. The Middle Passage is recorded to have accounted for between fifteen and twenty million deaths.³⁶ To appreciate the human cost of the slave trade one has to consider the estimates of world population reported by Rodney who indicated that from mid-17th to mid- 19th centuries, Africa's population stagnated while those of Asia and Europe nearly tripled. These stagnations could not be ascribed to any factor but the western European slave trade.³⁷ Moreover, it has been observed that about 27,000,000 slaves landed in America during the centuries the trade was actually booming. In addition, it has been estimated that for every slave that safely landed in America, one had died either during the raid, the march to the coast or on the slave ships.³⁸

However, some scholars who were at pains to mitigate or even justify the horrors which accompanied the most ubiquitous transactions in human history, have suggested a conservative estimate of 10 million slaves involved in the trade. They tried to dismiss earlier higher estimates as sheer guesswork based on unreliable figures.³⁹ Contestation over the number of slaves removed from Africa aside, it is an undeniable fact that several millions of Africans were placed on slave ships for export to the new world and Europe to provide the human labour required for the creation of capital that was invested to oil the machinery of Industrial Revolution in Europe.

Comparison of the African Diaspora Slaves in the Arab World with those of African Diaspora in the U.S

The status of slaves in the Arab world is largely influenced by the Islam's encouragement of manumission. Islam instituted a number of ways through which slaves in the Muslim world could become free and integrated into the society. The freeing of slaves is recommended as atonement for some wrong doings.⁴⁰ In addition, Islam recognised the alliance between free males and slave women, and the children from such union will like all free individuals prosper from the wealth of their father, and given right to inheritance.⁴¹ Moreover, Islam's prohibition of discrimination between peoples on account of the colour of their skin,⁴² made racism a non-issue in the Arab slave trade. This system allowed

for greater assimilation, hence the reality of physical African Diaspora in Arab lands is quite different from the African Diaspora in the Americas.

The Eastern and Western slave trade in Africa are different in several respects. Most important is that the treatment of slaves in the East is quite similar to their treatment at home in Africa. In the Arab Slave Trade, slaves were used mainly as domestic workers and soldiers, as there were no plantations or mines where the labour of millions of slaves was needed. But in contrast, the Atlantic Slave Trade was solely motivated by commercial incentives. Slaves were needed on the mines and plantations owned by Europeans. The slave trade was indeed an economic generator for Europe and her colonies. It was for this fact that Ali Mazrui ascribed the economic advancement of Western Europe to the slave trade.⁴³

Moreover, the western Trans-Atlantic slave traders were the most races conscious as they enslaved only Africans, but the Arabs enslaved both the blacks and whites from Europe and Asia.⁴⁴ Among the Arabs, Islam promoted manumission as a virtuous act; this provided the possibility for fortunate black slaves to regain their freedom. For example, during the early days of Islam we saw how an Ethiopian slave, Bilal secured his freedom upon the acceptance of Islam.⁴⁵ The prophet of Islam and the members of his household were reported to have freed more than 39,300 slaves.⁴⁶ No similar thing ever happened with the

slaves in the Americas. The profession of Christianity never became a source of liberty among Europeans; a slave remains perpetually a labourer to be exploited for economic gains. In fact, even the later abolition of slave trade was not as a result of any religious revival but as we shall see, it was informed by the changing economic needs of Europe.

Furthermore, among the Arabs as with all Muslim societies, the marriage of slave girls by freemen is allowed, and this union usually leads to the birth of free children with rights of inheritance and other rights. The mother also becomes *Ummul-walad* (mother of the child) with right far above ordinary slave woman and with a guarantee of freedom upon the death of her master.⁴⁷ Through this integrative process, discrimination based on race was de-emphasized. This is quite in contrast to what was obtained in America, where slaves were not allowed legal marriage and children were not raised among their parents (who were never formally united in union) rather they were often sold away.⁴⁸

In the Eastern part of the world among the Arabs, slaves did move up on the social ladder based on their parentage or even hard work. For example, a black African slave Abul Misk kafur al Ikhshidi rose to the position of the regent of Egypt (945-966 AD).⁴⁹ Similarly, Maad al Muntasir Billah, born in 1029AD to the caliph Azzahir and a slave mother Rasad, was declared successor to the caliphate. And having succeeded to the caliphate, his mother

Rasad, a Sudanese concubine, did exercise political power as regent.⁵⁰ Also, literate slaves did rise to influential positions in society as secretaries to the palace, ambassadors or military commanders. H. Salt travelling through Ethiopia observed that:

The situation of slaves is rather honourable than disgraceful.. .. And the difference between their state and that of western slaves is strikingly apparent. They have no long voyage to make, no violent change of habits to undergo, no Outdoor labour to perform no white man scorn to endure but on the contrary are frequently adopted like children within the family.⁵¹

But in the West, even after the emancipation laws, Blacks continued to be hunted by White terrorist groups such as the Ku Klux Klan (KKK) and Knight of White Camellia.⁵² The Colfax and Coshata Massacres of 1873 and 1874 in the southern states of America, where for every 3 whites killed 40 - 50 blacks were massacred was just one of the brutal assaults against Blacks.⁵³ In addition, the Jim Crow Laws of 1890's segregated all public facilities for the Blacks and Whites in the US.⁵⁴ In fact, even in religious circles, the African slaves or erstwhile slaves suffered hatred and segregation necessitating the establishment of African churches, such as the African Methodist Church of New York, the African Methodist Episcopal Zion Church established in 1816. Other

African Churches included: The first African Baptist Church in Savanna Georgia, the Saint Thomas African Episcopal Church, the Bethel African Methodist Episcopal Church in Philadelphia among others.⁵⁵ From this then, it could clearly be seen that, the western slavery bred racism, in contrast to the Eastern slave trade which brought about racial integration. This explained why, even today there are a number of offspring's of former African slaves that are now *bona fide* indigenes of Saudi Arabia and other Arab countries.

The Atlantic Slave Trade led to the loss of African sovereignty within its kingdoms. Most of the African kingdoms and states were occupied by the Europeans under the pretext of an effort to stop the slave trade. For example, Nigeria, Lagos was bombarded in 1851 under the guise of an attempt to unseat a slave trading king.⁵⁶ A similar reason was adduced for the removal of the Sarki of Kontagora.⁵⁷ But in the case of Arab slave trade it did not destroy African sovereignty. No African lands were seized and no Arab colonies were established as a result of this trade.

Furthermore, the Atlantic slave trade was unprecedented in terms of number of slaves involved in the traffic. Within a span of just about 4 centuries, several millions of Africans were transported outside the continent. On the contrast, the Eastern Slave Trade, despite the length of period within which it transpired 14th centuries the number of slaves involved is in no way comparable

to that of western European trade. In addition most of the slaves involved in the Arab African slave trade did work and serve in Africa and their descendants are still resident in Africa, unlike the victims of western slave trade that caused depredations and devastation of Africa.

Some Euro-Christian scholars, trying to paint the devil a saint, had given undue attention to the activities of the so-called Christian reformers who were said to have spearheaded the anti-slavery movement in Europe and North America, claiming that in the Muslim world there were no abolitionists.⁵⁸ But it is worth noting that the anti-slavery movement of the 18th and 19th century Europe had nothing to do with morality or human rights. It was a condition that was created by the changed economic environment of the time. Industrial Revolution made slave labour irrelevant and necessitated the hatching of new relationships in which Africa would continue to serve Europe's economic interest in a different way. Africa was turned into a producer of cheap cash crops, of raw materials due to the rising European industries. After colonization a new kind of slavery was created forced labour.

However, to deny the existence of opposition to the enslavement of people in the Muslim world is to say the least malicious. In the Senegal valley for example, at the end of the 17th century, the Toubenan Movement violently opposed the enslavement of people by some kings leading to the Marabour

War.⁵⁹ The founder of the movement Sheikh Nasir al-Din proclaimed that:

God does not permit kings to pillage, kill or enslave their peoples. He appointed them on the contrary to preserve their subjects and protect them from their enemies. People were not made for kings, but kings for the people.⁶⁰

On Reparation

Reparations or the making of amend for wrong or injustice meted out on nations has been the internationally recognised way of creating harmony and justice in the world system. It was out of this realization that Germany paid the Jews reparation for the Nazi Holocaust. The US government paid reparation to the American Japanese illegally interned during WW II in addition to a state apology.⁶¹ But Europe did not only pay nothing for the holocaust of African slavery but followed the slave trade with colonization for further exploitation. Herein lies the justification for African calls for reparation from European governments and merchant companies that benefited from the rape of Africa.⁶²

The debate for reparation for slavery starting from the US and other slave holding countries assumed some prominence in Africa when in 1990's, the OAU established the African Unity Group of Eminent Persons for Reparation co-chaired by Late Chief MKO Abiola and former UNESCO

Director General Ahmadu Mahtar M'bow.⁶³ The group did in 1993 convene the First African Conference on Reparation in Abuja. The Abuja Declaration called upon the international community to recognize that there is a unique and unprecedented moral debt owed to the African people. And the OAU was urged to call for full monetary repayment through capital transfer and debt cancellation.⁶⁴ Mazrui believed that reparation should be paid as a reward for Africa's long term contribution to the modern world.⁶⁵

The campaign for reparation was pushed further to become an item on the Agenda at the United Nations sponsored World Conference Against Racism, Racial discrimination, Xenophobia and Related Intolerance in Durban, September, 2001, the final document of the conference pointed out that: -

We acknowledge that slavery and slave trade ... are a crime against humanity and should have always been so ... victims of the violation of their human rights as a result of racism and related wrong should have the right to seek just and adequate reparation or satisfaction.⁶⁶

The European leaders however, refused to agree to an outright recognition of slave trade as a crime against humanity,⁶⁷ and made no commitment to the economic development of African nations as the US did in the Marshall Plan. This is a clear indication that

justice and international morality are opportunistically determined by political power relations. Because the descendants of slaves in Africa or in the global Africa Diaspora lack the political or economic power to pressure Europe as did the Jews and the Japanese, even an apology for a crime committed is not forth-coming from Europe not to talk of less of monetary repayment.

In an effort to legitimize the Euro - American world view, some European scholars and their lackeys have invented a number of deceitful explanations to discredit the whole idea of African reparation for slavery. H.L Gates sought to invert the slavery blame from Europe to Africa; he offered that the Africans in Africa were all villains and that the slave trade would not have happened without African complicity. Therefore, he argued, the considerable role of Africans on the slave trade makes figuring out who repayment should be extracted from an impossible task.⁶⁸

Another strategy adopted by these simpletons is Islamophobia. The mission of these militant defenders of Europe and America is to destroy any unity between Muslim Africa and the rest of Africa, thereby breaking the solidarity that is needed to pressure Europe for reparation. The path through which this mission could be accomplished has been clearly spelt out by one of them, as;

We have to try make the black people aware of the oppression and enslavement of blacks by

Muslims, especially Arabs, and particularly genocide that is going on in the Sudan for almost 50 years the Muslims were equal opportunity enslavers.⁶⁹

To further divert attention from the evils of European slave trade, these European apologists claimed that the Arabs slave trade did equally so much damage to Africa, and the Arabs unlike Europeans and Americans never physically recognised their role. In addition, unlike Europe and America that have given a number of grants to Africa, Arabs never attempted to offer any kind of grant. Therefore, they argued, it is more appropriate for the Africans to demand reparation from the Arabs than from Europe and America that have done so many good things to them.⁷⁰ But it is worth noting here that the so-called grants or aids that are being paraded around by this kind of literature are nothing more than efforts to secure markets and resources, as well as create a climate conducive for the permeation of imperialist capital, and its cultural variants.

Conclusion

The class of people that were termed as slaves in African societies were mostly used as domestic workers, soldiers or assistants in all other engagement of the master, and enjoy some rights such as raising a family and engaging in some economic pursuits. The eastern slave trade promoted by the Arabs did not alter this arrangement. And because of their

belief system slaves were treated in a much more humane manner than the later Atlantic Slave Trade. A number of slaves became free in the owners attempt to please God or as an atonement for a wrong done; and quite a number got the opportunity to move up on the social ladder to privileged positions with powers and rights far above some ordinary free men and women.

The Western slave trade on the other hand was quite different from all other earlier forms of slavery. It was selflessly pursued for the purpose of capitalism. Slaves were ruthlessly handled to produce sugarcane, tobacco, peanut, and cotton etc to provide capital for the industrial development of the West. The outcome of this relation was summed up by Gomez in one pithy sentence that "the emergence of the West was largely at the expense of African labour."⁷¹ The exploitation of African labour and other resources was further entrenched with the imperialist conquest and forceful domination of the continent. At independence, power was handed over to a class of rulers most favourable to western European interest. This, it is believed, will keep the nations open for the continued permeation of imperialist capital and the ransacking of the continent's resources

From what have been stated above it is clear that it was the western slave trade that undisputedly contributed most to the present situation in Africa. It permanently weakened the continent, led to its colonization by Europe and

engendered racism and contempt from which Africa still suffers. Therefore, in order to build an international moral community in which both sides trust each other in a relationship based on

solidarity, not merely on interest, the West must offer apologies and provide material compensation for its past exploitation and injustices meted on the people of the continent.

END NOTES

¹ Political positions found in many Northern Nigeria palaces, like Sarkin Gida, Wambai, Ubandawaki, Shantali, Bango and Barade are usually reserved for slave families. For more on this refer to J.E. Philips, 'Slavery on two Ribats in Kano and Sokoto' in P.E. Lovejoy (ed), *Slavery on the Frontiers of Islam, Production, Markers Wiener, 2004*. P.D. Curtin, 'The Atlantic Slave Trade 1600-1800' in *History of West Africa*, Vol. 1,(London, Longman 1960), 304-305.

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⁷ Ibid. P. 101

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²³ *New African*, No. 496, June, 2010 p. 22.

²⁴ B. Davidson & F .K Buah, *A History of West Africa 1000- 1800*,(London, Longman, 1965), 286-287.

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²⁶ Ibid.

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³⁰ W. Rodney, *How Europe Underdeveloped Africa* P. 105.

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³³ Within two centuries preceding the American Civil War, there were about 250 Slave uprisings which aim was personal freedoms, for refer "Slave rebellions" *Encyclopaedia Britannica* and E.M. Bokolo "The impact of Slave Trade on Africa", *Le monde Diplomatique*...

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